

Evaluation of Wind Field Reconstruction for Lidar- Assisted Control of a 2 MW Wind Turbine

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12.03.2025

CWD 2025, Aachen, Germany

Lidar-Assisted Control of Wind Turbines

Motivation

- ▶ wind is changing over space and time
- ▶ conventional control reacts after impact
- ▶ lidar technology provides wind preview
- ▶ better control performance is expected

Current Status of Lidar-Assisted Control

[Goldwind]

Status

- ▶ >2000 wind turbines (≈ 6 GW) running with LAC (Goldwind supported by sowento)
- ▶ Further industrial collaboration with SGRE, Movelaser etc.

Challenges

- ▶ complexity of economic benefit
- ▶ robustness / adaptivity
- ▶ certification

ABBA Project: Adaptive operating strategies for existing WTs

[Project description ABBA on enArgus, University website]

- ▶ Development, evaluation, and testing of adaptive operation and control strategies
- ▶ Integration of energy pricing, lidar-based wind forecasting, and load monitoring
- ▶ Lifetime extension, increase of energy yield, noise reduction, grid support
- ▶ Partners: FUAS, USTUTT, SGRE, sowento, DNV, ADC, Denker & Wulf

Evaluation of wind field reconstruction methods

- ▶ Current lidar systems provide unfiltered wind speed estimates at the measurement location.
- ▶ Filtering and timing is crucial for control!
- ▶ Improved algorithms in ABBA:
 - ▶ WETI: based on Simplified Navier Stokes
 - ▶ sowento: Moving-horizon and Space FIR
- ▶ Reference signal and status quo required!

Main questions

- ▶ How do we get a reference signal of the REWS with a known time offset?
- ▶ How good is the wind preview quality of the standard signals?
- ▶ How can we provide better wind preview signals?

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Wind field reconstruction

Control engineer's view

- ▶ Known input
- ▶ Measurable outputs
- ▶ Unknown disturbance
- ▶ Apply observer approach to reconstruct wind

Main challenge

- ▶ Limitation to line-of-sight v_{los}
- ▶ We cannot measure u, v, w
- ▶ But we can provide estimates with adequate wind (and lidar) models!
- ▶ Models depend on application

Baseline lidar data processing

Single distance WFR

- ▶ Measurements from one distance
- ▶ Assuming perfect alignment
- ▶ Using frozen turbulence

Multi distance WFR

- ▶ Measurements from all distances
- ▶ Time-shifting based on travel time
- ▶ Combination to one signal

Signal is then usually filtered and used in the feedforward (FF) controller with a preview time τ before the wind hits the rotor to overcome actuator reaction time.

Space FIR lidar data processing

sowento GmbH

Status

- ▶ For single/multi-distance
- ▶ Winner of IEA Wind summer games 2024
- ▶ Field testing soon in ABBA

Advantages

- ▶ FIR filter constant over space for given setup
- ▶ Easily tuned (width/height)
- ▶ Adaptive with quality
- ▶ Very robust!
- ▶ Ready-to-use signals!

Moving horizon lidar data processing

Conventional WFR

- ▶ Amount of preview time is unknown
- ▶ Preview time changes with wind speed
- ▶ Signal includes uncorrelated wind

Moving Horizon LDP

- ▶ Preview over fixed horizon for NMPC
- ▶ Condensed signal from all ranges
- ▶ Uncorrelated wind has been removed

More complex dynamic wind field reconstruction

Approaches using Navier-Stokes-Equations

- ▶ Unscented Kalman-Filter using simplified dynamic model based on NS [3]
- ▶ Training of physics-informed deep learning models using LES simulations [4]
- ▶ Wind-field characterization using proper orthogonal decomposition [2]

Rotor-effective wind speed from turbine data

Using a wind turbine as anemometer

$$J\dot{\Omega} = M_a - M_G r_{GB} \left(\frac{\Omega R}{v_0} \right)$$
$$\frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 \frac{c_p(\lambda, \theta)}{\Omega} v_0^3$$

- ▶ unknown rotor-effective wind speed
- ▶ measurable turbine data

Comparison over time

- ▶ Preview visible
- ▶ Larger trends similar
- ▶ Smaller details differ

Torque-balance wind speed estimator

- ▶ Typically applied in post-processing using phase-free filters for 3P etc., but also in real time [6].
- ▶ Requires solving cubic equation $\lambda^3 = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^5 \frac{c_p(\lambda, \theta)}{M_a} \Omega^2$ for given θ , Ω and $M_a = J\dot{\Omega} + M_{GrGB}$.
- ▶ Wind speed is then obtained by interpolation in 3D lookup table for current θ , Ω and M_a .
- ▶ Difficulties: finding the “right” λ , choosing bounds and discretization for θ , Ω and M_a .

Immersion and Invariance wind speed estimator

- ▶ SLOW model can be used to estimate the rotor speed from estimated wind speed and measured pitch angle and generator torque.
- ▶ A PI controller is then used to fit the estimated rotor speed to the measured one [7].
- ▶ Tuning very intuitive, closed-loop from v_0 to \hat{v}_0 can be hold (almost) constant to have same delay over full range of operation.

Closed-loop shaping

Calculate parameters of PI controller at each operation point with given dynamics

Closed-loop transfer function from v_0 to \hat{v}_0 vs. desired 2nd order linear model

$$\frac{K_P b_2 s + b_2 K_I}{s^2 + K_P b_2 s + b_2 K_I} \stackrel{!}{=} \frac{2D\omega s + \omega^2}{s^2 + 2D\omega s + \omega^2}$$

Solution

Proportional gain: $K_P = -\frac{2D\omega}{b_2}$ with Desired damping ratio: D
Integration time: $T_I = \frac{K_P}{K_I} = \frac{2D}{\omega}$ Desired angular frequency: ω

Rule of thumb

To avoid gain scheduling, set $b_2 = \left. \frac{\partial \dot{\Omega}}{\partial v_0} \right|_{OP}$ constant depending on rotor diameter, e.g. 0.02 rad/m/s for 126 m or 0.03 rad/m/s for 92 m

Results from WETI research turbine

Estimation of availability per beam

Availability: $\frac{3c(r)}{2\pi r}$ with cord length c , distance to hub r

Long Term Correlation Molas NL200

Results single distance LDP

- ▶ Correlation expressed by coherence between rotor and lidar
- ▶ Value crossing 0.5 used for Smallest Detectable Eddy Size
- ▶ Analytical coherence [8] is assuming wind evolution
- ▶ At 64 m better than expected $\approx 1.7D$
- ▶ At 120 m as expected: $\approx 3.4D$

First field testing results from last week!

Active LAC testing!

- ▶ Data from March 5 and 6
- ▶ Around 3 h with LAC and 3 h without above rated wind conditions
- ▶ Clear impact on generator speed spectra
- ▶ Similar wind conditions for both periods
- ▶ Now we are waiting for more wind!

Conclusions

Main questions

- ▶ How do we get a reference signal of the REWS with a known time offset?
 - ▶ How good is the wind preview quality of the standard signals?
 - ▶ How can we provide better wind preview signals?
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- ▶ From turbine signals with the “Immersion and Invariance” wind speed estimator
 - ▶ Required: rotor speed, pitch, generator torque and SLOW model with losses
 - ▶ Very easy to tune and constant time offset over operating range
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- ▶ Availability of the lidar is quite good, matches expectations
 - ▶ Wind preview quality is very good, mostly even better than expected
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- ▶ Ready-to-use signals for feedforward (Space FIR) or NMPC (Moving Horizon)
 - ▶ Use advanced methods such as POD, AI, Kalman filter with reduced Navier Stokes

Acknowledgment and References

This work is carried out as part of the ABBA project, funded by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action. ABBA: Adaptive Betriebsstrategien für bestehende Windenergieanlagen (FKZ 03EE3068A).

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Let your wind turbine see the
wind, you will be compensated!

Looking forward to your
questions and comments!

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